

Exact, Efficient, and Reliable Multi-Objective and Multi-Constrained IoT Workflow Scheduling in Edge-Hub-Cloud Cyber-Physical Systems Supplementary Material

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APPENDIX A

The main notations used in the manuscript are summarized in Table A.1.

TABLE A.1
MAIN NOTATIONS

Notation	Definition
\mathcal{U}	Set of devices in the considered edge-hub-cloud cyber-physical system (CPS).
$u_{\mu k}$	Device in \mathcal{U} , where μ indicates the type of the device (e=edge device, h=hub device, and c=cloud server) and k is the device index for the specific type (e.g., u_{e1} denotes edge device 1).
$\mathcal{P}_{\mu k}$	Set of reserved cores on device $u_{\mu k}$.
$p_{\mu k,q}$	Reserved core on device $u_{\mu k}$ (e.g., $p_{e1.1}$ denotes reserved core 1 on edge device 1).
$\lambda_{\mu k,q}$	Failure rate of core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
$\beta_{\mu k}$	Number of reserved cores on device $u_{\mu k}$ (i.e., $\beta_{\mu k} = \mathcal{P}_{\mu k} $).
\mathcal{P}	Set of all reserved cores on all system devices in \mathcal{U} .
$M_{\mu k}^{\text{bgt}}$	Memory budget for device $u_{\mu k}$.
$S_{\mu k}^{\text{bgt}}$	Storage budget for device $u_{\mu k}$.
$E_{\mu k}^{\text{bgt}}$	Energy budget for device $u_{\mu k}$.
$\psi_{\mu k,\nu l}$	Communication channel between devices $u_{\mu k}$ and $u_{\nu l}$.
$\epsilon_{\mu k,\nu l}$	Bandwidth of communication channel $\psi_{\mu k,\nu l}$.
$\pi_{\mu k,\nu l}$	Energy required to transmit a unit of data over communication channel $\psi_{\mu k,\nu l}$.
$\sigma_{\mu k,\nu l}$	Energy required to receive a unit of data over communication channel $\psi_{\mu k,\nu l}$.
$\mathcal{I}_{\mu k,\nu l}$	Set containing the device used for the communication between devices $u_{\mu k}$ and $u_{\nu l}$ when they cannot communicate directly.
\mathcal{C}	Set of sensing, actuating, or other device capabilities in the considered CPS.
c_a	Device capability in \mathcal{C} .
$\mathcal{C}_{\mu k}$	Set of capabilities of device $u_{\mu k}$ ($\mathcal{C}_{\mu k} \subseteq \mathcal{C}$).
$y_{\mu k}^{c_a}$	Binary parameter denoting whether device $u_{\mu k}$ has capability $c_a \in \mathcal{C}$.
\mathcal{T}	Set of tasks of the considered IoT workflow application.
τ_i	Task in \mathcal{T} .
$G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$	Initial task graph (TG) of the application, where \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{A} are the sets of its nodes and arcs, respectively.
N_i	Node in \mathcal{N} representing task $\tau_i \in \mathcal{T}$.
$A_{i \rightarrow j}$	Arc in \mathcal{A} representing the communication and precedence relationship between tasks $\tau_i, \tau_j \in \mathcal{T}$.
$z_i^{c_a}$	Binary parameter denoting whether task τ_i requires capability $c_a \in \mathcal{C}$.
L_{thr}	Predefined deadline before which the application should be completed (latency threshold).
$G' = (\mathcal{N}', \mathcal{A}')$	Intermediate task allocation graph (TAG), where \mathcal{N}' and \mathcal{A}' are the sets of its composite nodes and arcs, respectively.
N'_j	Composite node in \mathcal{N}' comprising a set of $N_{i,\mu k,q}$ nodes.
$N_{i,\mu k,q}$	Node in N'_j representing the possible allocation of task τ_i on core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
$A'_{i \rightarrow j}$	Composite arc in \mathcal{A}' comprising a set of $A_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}$ arcs.
$A_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}$	Arc in $A'_{i \rightarrow j}$ representing the transfer of data from node $N_{i,\mu k,q}$ to $N_{j,\nu l,r}$.

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TABLE A.1
MAIN NOTATIONS (CONT.)

Notation	Definition
M_i	Main memory required by task τ_i .
S_i	Storage required by task τ_i .
D_i	Output data size of task τ_i .
\mathcal{Q}_i	Set of child tasks of task τ_i .
ϕ_i	Binary parameter denoting whether task τ_i is an exit task.
$L_{i,\mu k,q}$	Execution time of task τ_i on core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
$P_{i,\mu k,q}$	Power required to execute task τ_i on core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
$E_{i,\mu k,q}$	Energy required to execute task τ_i on core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
$R_{i,\mu k,q}$	Reliability of task τ_i on core $p_{\mu k,q}$.
R_i^{thr}	Reliability threshold (lowest required reliability) of task τ_i .
$\zeta_{i,\mu k,q}$	Binary parameter denoting whether task τ_i when allocated on core $p_{\mu k,q}$ requires duplication.
$\theta_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}^{\xi m}$	Binary parameter denoting whether arc $A_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}$ involves indirect communication between devices $u_{\mu k}$ and $u_{\nu l}$ through device $u_{\xi m}$.
$CL_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}$	Time required to transfer output data D_i from task τ_i (allocated on $p_{\mu k,q}$) to task τ_j (allocated on $p_{\nu l,r}$).
$CE_{i,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,\nu l,r}$	Energy required to transfer output data D_i from task τ_i (allocated on $p_{\mu k,q}$) to task τ_j (allocated on $p_{\nu l,r}$).
$G'' = (\mathcal{N}'', \mathcal{A}'')$	Final extended task allocation graph (ETAG), where \mathcal{N}'' and \mathcal{A}'' are the sets of its composite nodes and arcs, respectively.
$\tau_{i,n}$	Primary (if $n = 1$) or replica (if $n = 2$) task of task τ_i .
N_i''	Composite node in \mathcal{N}'' consisting of subsets $N_{i,1}''$ and $N_{i,2}''$.
$N_{i,1}''$	Set of primary candidate nodes $N_{i,1,\mu k,q}$.
$N_{i,2}''$	Set of replica candidate nodes $N_{i,2,\mu k,q}$.
$N_{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Primary (if $n = 1$) or replica (if $n = 2$) candidate node in N_i'' representing the possible allocation of $\tau_{i,1}$ or $\tau_{i,2}$ on core $p_{\mu k,q}$, respectively.
$A_{i \rightarrow j}''$	Composite arc in \mathcal{A}'' comprising a set of $A_{i,n,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,o,\nu l,r}$ arcs.
$A_{i,n,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,o,\nu l,r}$	Arc in $A_{i \rightarrow j}''$ representing the transfer of data from candidate node $N_{i,n,\mu k,q}$ to $N_{j,o,\nu l,r}$.
$\hat{R}_{i,\mu k,q}$	Total reliability of task τ_i when its primary task $\tau_{i,1}$ is allocated on core $p_{\mu k,q}$, considering whether task duplication is required ($\hat{R}_{i,\mu k,q} = R_{i,\mu k,q,\nu l,r}$) or not ($\hat{R}_{i,\mu k,q} = R_{i,\mu k,q}$).
$R_{i,\mu k,q,\nu l,r}$	Total reliability of primary task $\tau_{i,1}$ and its replica $\tau_{i,2}$ when allocated on cores $p_{\mu k,q}$ and $p_{\nu l,r}$, respectively.
$x_{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Binary decision variable corresponding to candidate node $N_{i,n,\mu k,q} \in G''$.
$x_{i,n,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,o,\nu l,r}$	Binary decision variable corresponding to arc $A_{i,n,\mu k,q \rightarrow j,o,\nu l,r} \in G''$.
$t_{i,n}$	Continuous decision variable denoting the start time of task $\tau_{i,n}$ (corresponding to set $N_{i,n}'' \in G''$).
T	Continuous decision variable denoting the completion time of the application.
$x_{i,\mu k,q,\nu l,r}$	Auxiliary binary decision variable corresponding to candidate nodes $N_{i,1,\mu k,q}$ and $N_{i,2,\nu l,r}$ of task τ_i .
$x_{i,n,j,o}$	Auxiliary binary decision variable denoting whether task $\tau_{i,n}$ will be executed before task $\tau_{j,o}$.
$x_h^{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Auxiliary binary decision variable denoting whether task $\tau_{i,n}$ will be in execution on core $p_{\mu k,q}$ at time $s_h \in \mathcal{S}$.
$\hat{x}_h^{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Auxiliary binary decision variable used in conjunction with $x_h^{i,n,\mu k,q}$ to preserve the linearity of the model.
\mathcal{S}	Set of start times of all primary and replica tasks of the application.
s_h	Time instant in \mathcal{S} .
\hat{f}_{lat}	Normalized objective function of overall latency.
\hat{f}_{en}	Normalized objective function of overall energy.
\hat{f}_{rel}	Negated normalized objective function of overall reliability.
g	Multi-objective function comprising the weighted sum of \hat{f}_{lat} , \hat{f}_{en} , and \hat{f}_{rel} .
w_{lat}	Weight reflecting the relative importance of overall latency in g .
w_{en}	Weight reflecting the relative importance of overall energy in g .
w_{rel}	Weight reflecting the relative importance of overall reliability in g .
$\rho_{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Upward rank of candidate node $N_{i,n,\mu k,q} \in G''$. ¹
$EFT_{i,n,\mu k,q}$	Earliest finish time of candidate node $N_{i,n,\mu k,q} \in G''$. ¹

¹Used in extended HEFT.

APPENDIX B

Figs. B.1a and B.1b demonstrate the growth of ETAG nodes and arcs, respectively, under increasing TG size for synthetic IoT workflows. Figs. B.2a and B.2b illustrate the comparison between the average number of ETAG nodes and arcs, respectively, against their corresponding theoretical upper bounds under increasing TG size. The analysis of these results is provided in Section V-C2 of the manuscript.

Fig. B.1. ETAG (a) number of nodes and (b) number of arcs under increasing TG size. Box plots show the distribution of the number of nodes and arcs across ETAGs for each TG size, while the solid line connects the mean values.

Fig. B.2. ETAG (a) average number of nodes and (b) average number of arcs compared against their corresponding theoretical upper bounds under increasing TG size.